

Stereotyping: Impact to Hospitality and Tourism Students in Selected Higher Education Institutions in Dasmariñas, Cavite

Hannah Belle S. Estillore¹, Gabriel Louis S. Pelareja², Nathalie P. Poblete³,
Ms. Mary Daffodil B. Cordero⁴

^{1,2,3} Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management, DE LA SALLE UNIVERSITY – DASMARIÑAS

⁴ Adviser, DE LA SALLE UNIVERSITY – DASMARIÑAS

College of Tourism and Hospitality Management

Hospitality Management Department

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6602201>

Published Date: 01-June-2022

Abstract: Stereotyping has been a part of society to generalize what we think of different groups of people and although some are harmless, stereotypes can be seen as a negative way as well. Negative stereotypes can cause a multitude of effects to a student such as to their academic performance, self-esteem, and mental well-being which can influence them to not finish their college major and fulfill their dreams and shift to a different course altogether. This study focused on the effects of negative stereotyping and sorted them into three categories, psychological, academic, and career aspects. This thesis focused on the impact of stereotyping towards the Tourism and Hospitality students among selected higher education institutions in Dasmariñas, Cavite. The research is a qualitative research, purposive and convenience sampling techniques were used to identify the participants of the study. Narrative analysis is used in order to analyze and interpret the data gathered through interview, focus group discussion, and journals. Research shows that students knew about the stereotype and experienced it even before starting their college life. Although the stereotypes and discrimination somewhat affected the students at first, it was shown that the effect of stereotyping made them stronger and it didn't let it stop them. Therefore, we the researchers conclude that most of the students managed to cope with the effects of stereotyping caused by different people they have interacted with. The researchers proposed that the colleges should have a course encouragement seminar to motivate their student's to help them cope with the stereotypes.

Keywords: College, Hospitality, Stereotype, Student, Tourism.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background of the study

Our society is formed by people who are diverse and very different from each other; differences such as ethnicity, race, gender, age, social status are what make the world so unique. However, the diversity causes humans to stereotype, generalize, and form expectations about people based on the groups they belong to. While stereotyping is a part of a social environment, it is still problematic because it can lead to a false reputation and unreliable views of social groups (Beeghly, 2015). Although there are positive stereotypes that might be a flattering assumption about another person, there

are also negative stereotypes that can damage a student's perception on oneself or other people. These kinds of stereotypes are harmful to students because it directly impacts how they perform in school (Momentous Institute, 2017).

Since society and even popular culture in movies seem to reinforce stereotypes, college students are comfortable forming ideas on other degree programs based on stereotypes and label them negatively as a result. According to Chulick (2019), opinions such as Art majors having been born talented but in reality it took them years to practice their skills, English majors having perfect spelling, Math majors being seen as geeky and nerdy, STEM majors being money hungry, are just a few of the stereotypes college students experience in their degree programs, but they are far from the truth. Harvard Health Publishing (n.d.) states that the stereotype threat leads students to be self-conscious which can cause distractions, anxiety, and as well as interferes with achievements. Thus, applying this study to the students before they graduate into the workforce can be beneficial for them as well as erase preconceived notions on both Hospitality and Tourism industries.

Despite stereotyping being a "general" part of society, the Philippine government is actively trying to eradicate any discrimination and social stigma associated with it. A prime example of this is the Anti-Discrimination Act of 2017 which is a proposed law that sought to "[prohibit] discrimination on the basis of ethnicity, race, religion or belief, sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, gender expression, civil status and HIV status" (Ejercito, 2017). With all these in mind, the researchers decided to conduct a study that relates to the negative stereotypes experienced by tourism and hospitality management courses. This study provided an analysis to the impacts of these stereotypes to the students and aimed to raise awareness to help fight the stereotype threat that plagues these two degree programs. Although all students and programs experience stereotyping in general, the participants were chosen because it seems that hospitality and tourism programs have the most negative stereotypes surrounding them and because the researchers belong to one of the programs that are involved in this research. Hence, this research aims to find out the effects of negative stereotypes to these students.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the impact of stereotypes to the academic performances of the Hospitality and Tourism students of selected Higher Education Institutions and aims to provide answers for the following questions:

1. What are the negative stereotypes experienced by the participants?
2. What are the students' perceptions towards the negative stereotype?
3. What are the proper approaches and solutions to prevent the negative stereotype?

Specifically, this study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. To recognize the negative stereotype experienced by the participants.
2. To know the students' perceptions towards the negative stereotype they experienced.
3. To identify the factors that influence the negative stereotype
4. To determine the approaches and solutions to prevent the negative stereotype.
5. To know how the negative stereotype affects the students' perception towards their degree program and career decisions.

Conceptual Framework

The researchers used the Thematic Analysis model to have a better understanding on how the study was undertaken. In qualitative research, coding is a systematic process in which the collected data are condensed into analyzable units that are called "codes", which were further categorized and developed into themes. This coding process eventually helped the researchers build a general theoretical concept about the evidence gathered.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Stereotype

Stereotype threat can potentially harm students' attitudes and learning capabilities, students who experienced stereotypes have shown a decrease in enjoyment, persistence and disengagement with a domain of knowledge, the performance pressure due to stereotypes may lead the students falling farther and farther behind, this could have long-term implications, possibly affecting learning opportunities and career goals (Lyons et al., 2017).

The preconceived notion about the hospitality and tourism industries is that it is more of a temporary occupation rather than a stable career path, completely derailing the expectation of a young adult in having a healthy trajectory up an establishment (Tung, Tang, & King, 2018). This stereotype causes younger generations of employees to become impatient on climbing the ladder in their respective fields, waiting for a possible promotion that may never even happen for a very long time, thus they are more likely to leave the hospitality and tourism career path altogether instead of staying in their dream career (Smith, Clement, & Pitts, 2018).

According to Tung and King (2016), business students do not view hospitality and tourism management students as professionals. They are questioned what their profession actually is and whether there are professional designations because many business students disclosed that they were unfamiliar with these. They only recognize the mainstream specializations such as being a professional tour guide or hotel employee. Furthermore, the study found out that there are students who believe that the degree programs are easy choices because in the hospitality and tourism industry “you didn’t really need a degree to be a professional” and some also believe that you are qualified as long as you know how to cook and love to travel.

According to Monsanto (2020), stereotypes are not only evident in beauty, race or social class, but also in school. This is proven true especially to hospitality and tourism management students as they experienced being degraded concerning their cognitive ability with phrase like “that course is for stupid students”. Some people think that graduates of these two courses only become waitstaff, receptionists or a cook but they are not knowledgeable about how varied and complex the hospitality and tourism industry is and only judge because of stereotypes.

Discouragement

The perception of the students towards the degree programs they enrolled in became negative throughout the course of their college years, primarily because of negative experiences they went through during the on-the-job training and other external factors. By their final year the students were unsure and dispassionate about their program and career options, they felt discouraged because of the uncertainty of achieving a well-established career and preferred not to seek a profession related to their chosen degree program after they graduate (Kumar, Singh, Kumar, and Dahiya, 2015).

According to Anandhwanlert and Wattanasa (2016), although a high number of students would like to pursue and continue a career in Hospitality and Tourism industry, there is still a remarkable amount of Hospitality and Tourism students who would rather not continue and work in the industry after graduating. These students became uninterested and discouraged because of the nature of work and irregular working hours. The nature of work is seen as a disadvantage in working in the industry because of the negative experiences like maltreatment from customers or co-workers. On the other hand, the irregular working hours affect both social and family life.

3. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the research methods used in conducting the study and acted as an itinerary for researchers in achieving the goals in the journey of research. This section is subdivided into the following sections: research design, research locale, participants of the study and research sampling, research instrument and data gathering procedures, and data treatment and analysis.

Research Design

The researchers used qualitative research to conduct this study and utilized a semi-structured interview as well as journal entries on the participants from selected higher education institutions in gathering the data. Qualitative research design is applied to this study since it aims to get the perceptions and experiences of the participants. The researchers asked the participants about the impact surrounding the negative stereotype through interviews, focus group discussion and journals.

According to Haven and Grootel (2019), qualitative research uses language as its data, it can be in writing or spoken, it can also include images, videos, or other kinds of behavioral recordings. The qualitative data can be gathered through an interview, a focus group, or observation. Qualitative research aims to disclose the perceptions of the participants that the research question regards. It utilizes a process of integrating data analysis, preliminary review of data, and compilation of data. The use of data in qualitative research is the main asset of qualitative research in order to determine the direction the concept can go forward to use the data to produce theories and new research questions.

Qualitative research also aims to address questions that influence such social phenomena relating to social behavior and interpersonal interactions. Qualitative research has a strong ability to create an impact on rules, program development, and research procedures that are ideally appropriate to meet the desires of a population through having an understanding of the experiences and perceptions of various people and societies. All data gathering procedures require disclosing of human experience. By its very nature, the researchers will be empowered to learn about different participants' experiences surrounding the stereotype and use the data gathered to raise awareness and help eliminate the stereotype. (Jameel, Shaheen & Majid, 2018).

Research Locale

This study was conducted completely online because of the various community quarantines experienced by the respondents, as well as the cancellation of face-to-face classes due to the SARS-CoV-2 or Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. Before the cancellation of face-to-face classes the study was supposed to be conducted at three chosen Higher Education Institutions in Dasmariñas, Cavite; namely De La Salle University – Dasmariñas, Emilio Aguinaldo College – Cavite Campus, and Brookfield College, because of their respective Hospitality and Tourism

programs; despite this, the study still had the same respondents and utilized Zoom Video Communications for the interviews and focus group discussion and Google Docs for the journal entries.

Participants of the Study and Research Sampling

The participants of the study were the 3rd Year Hospitality and Tourism Management students from the selected higher education institutions in Dasmariñas City. Specifically, eight students from three different institutions were chosen; four students from the tourism management department and four students from the hospitality management department, totaling it into twenty-four participants.

The three higher education institutions were chosen because they are all situated in Dasmariñas City, Cavite and proximity among these institutions were highly considered during the conceptualization of the study before the pandemic. Another consideration is that all these institutions offer the courses that are considered in the study. Connections among the researchers and the students in these institutions are strong that easy communication in conducting the study is expected to be smooth and hassle-free. While, the criteria that was used in choosing the participants are their college degree program, year, and time of availability.

In this matter, the researcher used the purposive sampling technique and convenience sampling technique in choosing the participants. Purposive sampling is also known as judgmental, selective or subjective sampling. Purposive sampling relies on the judgment of the researcher when it comes to selecting: people, organizations, events or pieces of data that are to be studied (Crossman, 2017). The goal of purposive sampling is to focus on a characteristic of a population that is of interest, which will best enable you to answer the researchers' questions.

Convenience sampling is a kind of sampling method that puts emphasis on generalizability, it is a nonrandom type of sampling that determines the participants within the target population that meets a certain criteria, such as time availability, accessibility, geographical proximity and the willingness to partake in the study (Etikan, 2016).

Research Instrument & Data Gathering Procedures

For this study, the researchers used one-on-one interviews with the participants online and semi-structured questions were used as a guide. Interviews allowed the interviewer to initiate a discussion with the participants by asking open-ended question rather than just following a formalized list of questions, a semi-structured interview allows flexibility in manipulating certain variables, validating it as an ideal method of data collection for qualitative studies (Adhabi & Anozie, 2017).

Chosen participants were also chosen to take part in a focus group discussion online. Merriam & Tisdell (2017) states that focus group discussion allows the participants to be relaxed and allows them to give ideas freely and comfortable. It will help the researchers to get meaty information coming from them.

The journal of the participants is the third source of data that completed the triangulation which is an important aspect in qualitative research (Creswell, 2018). Chosen participants were asked to write their journals expressing their experiences on being in the field of hospitality management or tourism management. Their expression of feelings of ups and downs, their sentiments, and victories were asked and documented in their journal entries.

Triangulation in qualitative research is very important as one or two sources of data are not enough to get the whole meaning of the respondent's experiences. This is the main reason why three sources of data were gathered – interview, focus group discussion and journal (Merriam & Tisdell, 2017; Creswell, 2018).

The researchers sent a consent form to the student council presidents from the Hospitality and Tourism departments of each institution through Facebook Messenger and each president gave the researchers the list of participants they gathered from their respective colleges. The time of the interview, focus group discussion and deadline of the journal entries were arranged according to each participant's schedules. The utilization of Zoom and other online platforms offer flexibility, convenient participation and preservation of data quality, one of the key advantages is that online interviews can be recorded; this allows the researchers to easily manage and secure the data (Archibald et al., 2019).

The participants had the privilege to express their opinions and experiences and their answers were treated with confidentiality and interviewer neutrality, the data was gathered with an interview recording using the Purposive Sampling Technique.

Data Treatment and Analysis

The researchers used a narrative analysis in this study, wherein the transcripts, notes and recordings were written to synthesize the ideas of the respondents that were gathered. According to Allen (2017), narrative analysis is when researchers interpret stories that were told during the interview and then form meaningful interpretations on different elements from the participant's experiences and actions thus forming an understanding on these events.

After transcribing the interview, the researchers coded the data with the use of the inductive method. Inductive research coding is the conversion of raw qualitative data like the interview into useful quantitative data and allowing a theory to emerge from the content gathered from the data (Streefkerk, 2019). Specifically, the codes that were used were determined by the participant's answers during the interview.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the findings and outcome of the research done to the Tourism and Hospitality students of Selected Higher Education Institutions in Dasmariñas, Cavite. There were 24 participants of the study, who were chosen because of their college program, university or college, year level and time of availability. The discussion focused on the different effects of stereotyping and discrimination to the students because of the stereotypes that were attached to their degree program. This section begins with negative stereotypes experienced by the students followed by the effect of stereotyping and ends with stereotypes in the point of view of the students.

SOP 1. What are the negative stereotypes experienced by the participants?

There are two themes that emerged: HRM and BTM are low quality degrees; and taking HRM and BTM degrees does not need so much intelligence.

- **Theme 1: HRM and BTM are low quality degrees**

The Respondents explained that they felt low about themselves at times because of what they heard from people; these include strangers, friends, or even family members.

Respondent 2 stated that, *"parang iniisip ng ibang tao na hindi ka magaling or matalino sa HRM ka babagsak, sinasabi ng ibang tao, "Ay HRM lang course mo ganon? Diba puro luto lang naman kayo"* [*"other people think that you aren't good or smart enough so you wound up in HRM, they say that, "Oh your course is just HRM? Aren't you just cooking"*].

While Respondent 4 stated that, *"Since sinasabi ng iba na pag grumaduate ka as Tourism Managament student magiging flight attendant ka, ang iniisip nang iba is "ay ano lang Tourism ka lang? mag aano ka lang sa airport"* [*"Since other people say that when you graduate in Tourism Management you automatically will become a flight attendant, so they think that "oh you're just a Tourism graduate? You're just going to lounge around an airport"*].

Stereotyping has long been an issue not only regarding beauty, race and social class. Stereotype can also happen in the world of academics, there are those individuals who are being looked down because of pursuing a degree in Hospitality and Tourism, there are people who make and spread negative comments and stereotype regarding the HRM and Tourism courses, some students are being questioned and degraded in terms of their cognitive abilities as compared to students of other courses. (Mansanto, 2020).

- **Theme 2: Taking HRM and BTM degrees do not need so much intelligence.**

Respondents said that based on what they heard from people around them, they feel that many of them think that HRM and BTM degrees do not need so much intelligence.

Respondent 21 said that she had experienced the stereotype with the course she was in, *"People will try to make a conversation with me asking me about my course and the usual comments are "Diba madali lang naman course mo?", "Puro luto lang naman yan eh, hindi naman kailangan magbayad ng malaki para lang matuto magluto", and of course the typical "Puro babagsakin lang naman yung nasa course niyo."*

[*"...and the usual comments are "Isn't your course super easy?", "It's just cooking, you don't need to pay a big tuition just to learn how to cook", and of course the typical "Your course is just full of failing students."*]

While Respondent 17 stated that when he was in college, *“I was really stressed and my classmate was looking at me like in a judgmental way and he was saying “why are you even complaining or worrying about your college life, HRM is the easiest course.”*

Stereotyping has always been a problem during university years as people often tend to see you as the degree program you take rather than the person you are. There are a lot of people in university that generalize the degree program a person is in and unfairly judge them for a stereotype they could not control such as an Education degree being “feminine” and a Hospitality degree being “non-intelligent” individuals. (Chulick, 2019).

SOP 2. What are the students’ perceptions towards the negative stereotypes?

There are three themes that emerged: Stereotyping among HRM and BTM having Psychological effects; Stereotyping among HRM and BTM having academic effects; and Stereotyping among HRM and BTM having career effects.

• Theme 1: Stereotyping among HRM and BTM has Psychological Effects

Most of the Respondents answered that the stereotype affected their psychological well-being or self-esteem in a positive way.

Respondent 23 stated that, *“Having those stereotyping doesn’t affect my grades or my psychological wellbeing, because I know that those words are for boosting or proving them that they are wrong.”*

Respondent 7 stated that, *“Honestly siguro I just laugh it out, at the end of the day, I don’t think they know how hard it is for us to study what we’re doing.”*

While Respondent 11 stated that, *“Positive po, kasi kailangan po nating patunayan sa ibang tao na mali yung sinasabi nila sa mga nagtake ng course na to”*

[“Positive, because we need to prove to other people that the things they’re saying about Tourism and HRM courses are wrong”].

According to Harvard Health Publishing (n.d.), there are several ways to counteract or avoid being affected by the stereotypes, individuals can develop self-awareness and treat the stereotype as a means to motivate and remind themselves that they are not the cause of the stereotype, and that the stereotype can be considered as a social condition that can help individuals to disassociate themselves from the stereotyped group and achieve a sense of individuality.

• Theme 2: Stereotyping among HRM and BTM has Academic Effects

When asked if the negative stereotypes affect their academic performance, the majority of the respondents said that it didn’t affect them at all.

Respondent 1 as she said that, *“Yun nga, as I said before, hindi din. Kasi dapat hindi ka nagpapa-apekto lalo na academic yan kasi gusto mo naman yung course na to at gagawin mo to ng tama. Kaya hindi naapektuhan academic performance ko.”*

[“As I’ve said before, no. Because you shouldn’t let yourself be affected because this is for our academics and you really like your course and you will finish it rightfully. That’s why my academic performance isn’t affected”].

Respondent 24 answered in her journal that she only got used to the stereotype because of constantly hearing it and that is why it didn’t affect her, *“It affected my grades, in such a way and my confidence was gone, I am afraid to take things and participate in some activities. I sometimes feel lazy to go to school because for me I don’t belong there. But in the end, I realized that my life doesn’t depend on others’ opinions and I can be better. I just learned how to not get affected by what’s happening.”*

According to Lyons et al. (2017) stereotyping experienced by young students greatly diminished their enjoyment in learning. Students who also experienced discrimination said that it affected their want to study in class and this causes an impact to their academic career that persisted even into the next grade level.

When the participants were asked if they felt any discouragement to continue their course, some say that they got discouraged but they still managed to continue their journey towards graduation,

Respondent 6 mentioned that the COVID-19 Pandemic and the uncertainty of careers in her industry made her discouraged in continuing her course, *“May part sakin na oo, may part sakin na hindi. Lalo na ngayong nagkaroon ng pandemic na hindi natin in-expect mangyari, lalo na sa Hospitality Industry affected lahat ma-pa restaurant, ma-pa cruise, hotel, landbase apektado talaga at bawal physical contact kahit kanino. Apektado pa mga employee, apektado din guest at customer mo at doon ako na discourage noong una pero ngayon makakabangon naman tayo kaya okay naman ako na ituloy tong course kahit closed yung industry natin ngayon... babangon din tayo.”*

[“There’s a part of me that wants to stop but there’s also a part of me that wants to continue. Especially there’s a pandemic that we never really expected, the biggest one to be affected is the Hospitality Industry, the restaurants, cruises, landbase, it’s all affect and no physical contact is allowed between people. Employees are also affected, along with the guests and customers and that’s where I was discouraged at first but now that we’re rising up in the pandemic, I’m okay continuing this course even though our industry is closed... we will rise again”].

The reasons why college students feel discouraged in continuing their chosen course and shifting to a different one are grouped into three categories mainly, personal and course preferences, influential issues from family and others and future career issues. (Jaradat, 2017)

- **Theme 3: Stereotyping among HRM and BTM has Career Effects**

When asked if they think the stereotype will affect their future career, most of the respondents answered no or that it will affect them in a positive way, and a few answered that it will affect them negatively.

Respondent 3 stated that, *“For me hindi, pag sinunod mo yung gusto mo sa buhay, hindi ka magkakaroon ng regrets, hindi ka magkakaroon ng discouragement, as long as masaya ka sa mga ginagawa mo.”*

[“For me not really, if you follow your passion in life, you won’t have any regrets, you won’t get discouraged, as long as you are happy in what work you have”].

Respondent 17 stated that, *“To be honest, I don’t really think it will affect me, because you know you gotta admit it’s everywhere, criticism is everywhere, I’m so used to it that it doesn’t affect me anymore and you know yourself better than anyone else.”*

Meanwhile, some negative responses like Respondent 18 answered, *“For me siguro, makaka-affect sayo yun lalo na sa work, sa performance mo in the future, lalo na kung sensitive yung isang tao, yung isang Tourism or HRM student na di kayang maghandle ng pressure lalo na sa ganitong industry marami talagang criticism na sinasabi yung ibang tao.”*

[“For me I think that we would get affected work wise in your performance in the future, especially if you are a sensitive person. Tourism and HRM workers face criticisms that people say daily, and some student’s might not handle the pressure in the future”].

According to Smith (2016), studies have proven that stereotype threat can reduce the performance of an individual, people who experience stereotype can result to low self-esteem and disengagement in their work, some of the effects can be, anxiety, reduced effort and lower creativity and motivation, but there are ways to identify and counteract the stereotype threat, building up awareness and raising the morale of the employees can lessen its effects.

SOP 3. What are the proper approaches and solutions to prevent the negative stereotypes?

There are three themes that emerged: The school’s role in preventing negative stereotypes; the teacher’s role in preventing negative stereotypes; and the student’s role in preventing negative stereotypes.

- **Theme 1: The school’s role in preventing negative stereotypes**

The Respondents explained that preventing negative stereotypes among degree programs should be endorsed by the college / university itself.

Respondent 4 stated that elementary and high school teachers must help build up the character and aims of their students and avoid stereotyping. She stated *“Dapat sa school palang ini-encourage na yung mga bata na kahit anong course i-take nila, meron silang magiging parte sa industriya, walang mababa or mataas na sweldo, para din maiwasan yung stereotype.”*

[“School’s should start encouraging young student’s that whatever course they take, they will have a part in an industry, there is no low or high paying job, so that stereotyping would be prevented.”]

Respondent 9 mentioned that the school aspect will play an important role to remove the mindset of students that the tourism and hospitality courses are easy courses and suggested that *“dapat i-orient na sila na hindi ganoon kadali yung course natin at yung mga trabahong gagampanan natin, at hindi lang tayo magluluto”* [*“they should have an orientation that emphasizes that the course and future jobs they picked isn’t that easy and we aren’t just cooks”*].

While teachers may have little immediate authority over these processes, there is still possibility for improvement and change at the school and teacher levels. Individuals may combat their own stereotype tendencies, according to research, by first being aware that these cognitive shortcuts are occurring. Teachers may then confront their own subconscious with this knowledge, and schools can ensure that biased judgments of students are avoided. (Campbell, n.d.).

- **Theme 2: The teacher’s role in preventing negative stereotypes**

The Respondents said that the teachers / professor’s should also guide their students on what stereotyping is and help the student’s understand that stereotyping is a bad thing spread or think upon.

Respondent 3 stated that *“mas maganda na maiwasan or magkaroon ng possible solution is turuan yung mga bata, yung mga elementary, high school, senior high school and college na sa lahat ng kursong pagpipiliian like Hospitality or Tourism is both lang silang may advantage, na kung saan may magandang benefits silang makukuha dun sa bawat kursong pipiliin nila like Tourism and Hospitality.”*

[*“it is appropriate to prevent or a possible solution is teach students, from elementary, high school, senior high school. And even college that all degree programs like Hospitality or Tourism, all of them have advantages, that the degree they would like to pursue have different benefits.”*]

While Respondent 4 stated that *“Siguro dapat high school palang or as early as elementary, dapat ibuild yung character or aims ng mga bata, dapat yung mga teacher i-explain din sa mga bata as early as that na kung anu yung gusto nilang pangarap na maging trabaho dapat ipursue nila, kasi before hindi naman sa nilalahat ko yung mga teacher, may iba lang din akong nakitang teacher before na ganun yung mindset na “wag ka mag ganitong course kasi mababa sweldo”.*

[*“I think that during high school or as early as elementary, teachers should build the character or the aims of the young students, the teachers should explain that no matter what your dream they should pursue that dream as their career. Because I saw some teacher’s before that they have this mindset of “don’t take this degree, it has a low salary” and it shouldn’t be like that.”*]

Teachers don’t always have a voice in decisions made in school however they do have a lot of control over what occurs in the classroom and whether all of the students feel welcomed, secure, and successful. They have the ability to address prejudices that affect students throughout the school day and aim to eliminate stereotype threats. (Wing & Gross, 2021).

- **Theme 3: The student’s role in preventing negative stereotypes**

Lastly, the Respondents also stated that they themselves as student’s should know what to do in preventing the negative stereotypes as they are enrolled in HRM or BTM themselves and should know better.

Respondent 18 suggested they should educate people especially those who stereotype and stated *“kahit papaano may idea sila at maeducate, especially yung mga sa ibang courses.”*

[*“atleast they have a small idea, and they would get educated, especially other courses”*].

Another solution he said is to raise awareness because *“pare-parehas lang rin naman tayong students na nagpu-pursue ng dreams”*

[*“we are all students that are just pursuing our dreams”*].

Respondent 6 stated that *“Siguro pwede nating i-promote yung mga iba’t ibang subject ng HRM na hindi pagluluto. Yung stigma tanggalin na natin agad at ipakita natin yung mga capability ng mga HRM students and course”.*

[*“I think we should promote the different subjects that are included in the HRM degree, that it’s not just cooking. The stigma should be removed right away and we should show our capabilities as HRM students.”*]

Although some stereotypes can seem accurate, students are humans, and no one ever falls perfectly into any stereotypical image. On the other hand, it would be better for students to accept the similarities they have with others to connect and create friendships and they shouldn’t let assumptions deter any student from achieving a degree that best suits them. (Dumbauld, 2017).

5. CONCLUSION

Going to college to take a degree is a dream of every senior high school graduate. Yet, it is a fact that most of the students already know the negative statements about the course they are going into even before enrolling to it. It is usual for first year college freshmen to be affected by these stereotypes and the result is them being discouraged from continuing the course until they graduate. Therefore, the researchers conclude that even though the students are aware of the comments of other people, it still affects them in some way, which is caused by their interactions from social media, friends, and even relatives.

However, the results of this study also show that amid the challenges faced by HRM and BTM students, they manage to see their situation in a different perspective. The students didn't let the stigma bother them, their grades, and their future careers, and they continue to study despite the stereotype still being present in their everyday lives.

College students are the future of our society, and as young adults they developed their own way of dealing with the negative statements. Hence, stereotypes and its effects to students should not be taken lightly, in order to help with this issue, colleges and universities should make the necessary actions to help their students and keep them passionate and dedicated in their chosen field.

6. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the research, the researchers recommend that higher education institutions create identity safe classrooms; this is by making an environment where students will matter as individuals regardless of their course or degree and is assured that they are valued and acknowledged.

Colleges should raise awareness by forewarning students about stereotyping and how it can affect an individual's emotional or psychological well-being, those stereotyped groups that are being affected should be offered help. The HRM and BTM departments of every institution should conduct seminars to their freshmen and sophomore students at the start and end of the school year in collaboration with the guidance counselor's office, along with other students regardless of their year, who may be victims of stereotyping to educate them.

The colleges should also encourage their students by priming positive images. When students could potentially be affected by a stereotype threat, teachers along with other students should motivate and inspire others by raising their morale, whether it is by giving advice, giving positive thoughts and compliments. Every person has their own struggles and how they cope with it, whether it's about their personal life or their academic life, the best way to prevent stereotype from affecting students is to get rid of biases and misconceptions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Adhabi, E., & Anozie, C. B. (2017). Literature review for the type of interview in qualitative research. *International Journal of Education*, 9(3), 86-97
- [2] Allen, M. (2017). *The sage encyclopedia of communication research methods* (Vols. 1-4). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc doi: 10.4135/9781483381411
- [3] Anandhwanlert, T., & Wattanasan, C. (2016). Career Perception of Undergraduate Students on Tourism and Hospitality Industry in Thailand. *Career Perception of Undergraduate Students on Tourism and Hospitality Industry in Thailand*, 5(10), 339-346.
- [4] Anti-Discrimination Act of 2017, S. 1619, 117th Cong. (2017) http://legacy.senate.gov/ph/lis/bill_res.aspx?congress=117&q=SBN-1619
- [5] Archibald, M. M., Ambagtsheer, R. C., Casey, M. G., & Lawless, M. (2019). Using Zoom Videoconferencing for Qualitative Data Collection: Perceptions and Experiences of Researchers and Participants. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406919874596>
- [6] Beeghly, E. (2015). What is a Stereotype? What is Stereotyping? *Hypatia*, 30(4), 675-691. doi:10.1111/hypa.12170
- [7] Campbell, T. (n.d.). *Assessment vicious cycle – how susceptible are primary teachers to subconscious stereotyping?* Teachwire. Retrieved from <https://www.teachwire.net/news/stereotyped-at-7-can-teacher-judgements-be-subconsciously-based-on-gender-s>

- [8] Chulick, G. (2019, May 08). The Issue of College Major Stereotyping: Will This Epidemic End? Retrieved October 04, 2020, from <https://medium.com/@gabbychulick/the-issue-of-college-major-stereotyping-will-this-epidemic-end-180e2496d30e>
- [9] Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications.
- [10] Crossman, A. (2020, March 19). What You Need to Understand About Purposive Sampling. Retrieved from <https://www.thoughtco.com/purposive-sampling-3026727>
- [11] Dumbauld, Beth. (26 May 2017) "Are College Major Stereotypes True?" *StraighterLine* Retrieved from www.straighterline.com/blog/are-college-major-stereotypes-true/
- [12] Edelson, David. (14 Oct. 2016) "How Do College Graduates Benefit Society at Large?" *Association of Public & Land-Grant Universities* www.aplu.org/projects-and-initiatives/college-costs-tuition-and-financial-aid/publicvalues/societal-benefits.html
- [13] Etikan, I. (2016). Comparison of Convenience Sampling and Purposive Sampling. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics* 5(1):1. doi:10.11648/j.ajtas.20160501.11
- [14] Gohu, K. (2019, October 08). Change of plans: Shiftees' Stories. Retrieved from <https://www.review.ahead.edu.ph/change-of-plans-shifting-courses/>
- [15] Haven, T. L., & Grootel, D. L. (2019). Preregistering qualitative research. *Accountability in Research*, 26(3), 229-244. doi:10.1080/08989621.2019.1580147
- [16] Jameel, B., Shaheen, S., & Majid, U. (2018). Introduction to Qualitative Research for Novice Investigators. *Undergraduate Research in Natural and Clinical Science and Technology (URNCST) Journal*, 2(6), 1-6. doi:10.26685/urncst.57
- [17] Janghorban, R., Roudsari, R. L., & Taghipour, A. (2014). Skype interviewing: The new generation of online synchronous interview in qualitative research. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-being*, 9(1), 24152. doi:10.3402/qhw.v9.24152
- [18] Jaradat, M. (2017). Reasons influence students' decisions to change college majors. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 7(3), 223-238.
- [19] Kumar, A., Singh, P. K., Kumar, A., & Dahiya, S. (2015). Changing Perception of Students toward Hospitality Industry: A Comparative Analysis. *International Journal of Tourism & Hospitality Reviews*, 1(1), 07. doi:10.18510/ijthr.2014.112
- [20] Landis, L. (2020, April 30). Five Reasons Students Regret Their College Choice. Retrieved from <https://supertutortv.com/videos/five-reasons-students-regret-their-college-choice/>
- [21] Lyons, E. M., Simms, N., Begolli, K. N., & Richland, L. E. (2017). Stereotype Threat Effects on Learning From a Cognitively Demanding Mathematics Lesson. *Cognitive Science*, 42(2), 678-690. doi:10.1111/cogs.12558
- [22] Mental Health & Stereotyping: Another danger of stereotyping (n.d.). Retrieved from https://www.health.harvard.edu/press_releases/mental_health_stereotyping
- [23] Merriam, S. B., & Tisdell, E. J. (2017). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*.
- [24] Momentous Institute. (2017, October 17). Why Stereotypes Are Harmful. Retrieved from <https://momentousinstitute.org/blog/why-stereotypes-are-harmful>
- [25] Monsanto, Ram. (2020, February 16). Stereotyping does not only happen when we talk about beauty, race and social class, among others. [Facebook post]. Retrieved from <https://www.facebook.com/roelmonsanto/posts/3501139139928094>
- [26] Selby, B. (2020, July 14). Should Parents Have an Active Role in Their Student's Major? Retrieved from <https://www.collegeraptor.com/find-colleges/articles/college-majors-minors/should-parents-have-an-active-role-in-choosing-their-students-college-major/>

- [27] Smith, S. (2016, February 18). Stereotype Threat in the Workplace: What Your Business Should Know. Retrieved from <https://www.opensesame.com/site/blog/stereotype-threat-workplace-what-your-business-should-know/>
- [28] Smith, W. W., Clement, J. C., & Pitts, R. E. (2017). Oh the places they'll go. Examining the early career path of hospitality alumni. *Journal of Teaching in Travel & Tourism*, 18(2), 109-122. doi:10.1080/15313220.2017.1416726
- [29] Stereotype Threat in the Workplace: What Your Business Should Know. (2021, January 22). Retrieved from <https://www.opensesame.com/site/blog/stereotype-threat-workplace-what-your-business-should-know/>
- [30] Streefkerk, R. (2019, November 11). Inductive vs. Deductive Research Approach. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/inductive-deductive-reasoning/>
- [31] Tung, V. W., & King, B. (2016). The stereotyping of tourism management students in a business school setting. *Journal of Teaching in Travel & Tourism*, 16(1), 60-77. doi:10.1080/15313220.2015.1116423
- [32] Tung, V. W., Tang, M. F., & King, B. E. (2018). Tourism industry career prospects and the business environment: Evidence from Canada and Macau. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 20(4), 518-525. doi:10.1002/jtr.2201
- [33] Wing, K., & Gross, M. (2021, October 6). *How to recognize, avoid, and stop stereotype threat in your class this school year*. Digital Promise. Retrieved from <https://digitalpromise.org/2018/08/16/recognize-avoid-stop-stereotype-threat-class-school-year/>